

Do AI Models Remember History? Representing Phantom Borders in Large Language Models

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Abstract

Phantom borders are historical borders that, although they no longer exist officially or politically, their traces are still visible. These borders challenge the fundamental geographic assumption of spatial dependence. While prior research has documented the persistence of phantom borders in socioeconomic and political data, it remains unclear whether large language models (LLMs) inherently capture and reproduce these underlying spatial boundaries. Using the former East–West German divide as a phantom border, this study investigates the capability of various LLMs—particularly GPT-5.4, GPT-4o, Gemini-3.1-pro-preview, Gemini-2-flash, DeepSeek-v4-pro, and DeepSeek-chat—in representing the phantom borders. Using NUTS-3 regional units, we ask LLMs to classify each region as belonging to East or West Germany. In parallel, we compare region-name embeddings to the concepts “East Germany” and “West Germany” using the `text-embedding-3-large` model. Our results reveal that recent LLMs can represent the division with perfect accuracy, while earlier versions show limitations. The embedding-based analysis further uncovers a spatial gradient without a clear discontinuity aligned with the historical border. These findings suggest that LLMs implicitly encode historically contingent spatial structures, highlighting both their potential for geographic representation and the risk of reproducing outdated or biased spatial representations.

Keywords

Phantom Borders, Foundation Models, Embedding Similarity, Generative AI Memorization.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) systems have changed many downstream tasks such as information retrieval, question-answering, and recommendation systems [1]. In particular, the emergence of generative information retrieval and large language models (LLMs) has introduced new paradigms that go beyond traditional keyword matching toward direct answer generation and improved personalization [2]. As a result, people increasingly interact with language agents every day to ask about their daily needs and get quick, conversational responses to their questions [3].

LLMs, trained on vast amounts of unstructured world knowledge, learn rich semantic representations that implicitly encode geographic, cultural, and historical knowledge [4]. They can reproduce aspects of human spatial reasoning and geographic understanding [5, 6, 7]. However, it remains unclear whether they also capture historical phenomena such as phantom borders—historical boundaries that continue to shape spatial patterns such as demographic, economic, and cultural characteristics even when they formally disappear [8, 9]. This raises an important question: **Do LLMs internalize and reproduce historical spatial divisions, even when these divisions no longer exist in formal administrative structures?**

By focusing on the former East–West German border, which lasted from 1949 to 1990 [10], the task goes beyond a simple geographic lookup, as this division is no longer reflected in current administrative structures. Using NUTS-3 region names, we evaluate whether LLMs can correctly classify regions as belonging to East or West Germany. In addition, we compute the similarity between region-name

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Listing 1: The user prompt for our experiment

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Determine whether the region {name} is located in West Germany (W) or East Germany (E). Respond with ONLY one letter: W or E.
```

embeddings and the concepts “East Germany” and “West Germany,” to assess whether semantic representations encode similar patterns. By proposing a systematic prompt-based classification approach and an embedding analysis, this study provides a novel perspective on how foundation models (FMs) encode geographic knowledge. More broadly, it contributes to GeoAI research, raising critical concerns about bias, knowledge representation, and the presence of historical structures in data-driven models.

2. Data and Methods

The analysis focuses on Germany at the NUTS-3 level, which provides a suitable spatial resolution for detecting regional discontinuities of the East–West division. Each region is labeled according to its historical affiliation with either East Germany (German Democratic Republic, GDR) or West Germany (Federal Republic of Germany, FRG). Region names are provided in their official German form.

2.1. LLM-Based Classification

To assess whether LLMs encode the phantom border, we conduct a controlled prompting experiment using several models ranging from earlier to more recent versions including GPT-5.4, GPT-4o, Gemini-3.1-pro-preview, Gemini-2-flash, DeepSeek-v4-pro, and DeepSeek-chat. We selected a diverse set of models to capture differences in their knowledge representation. Each model is prompted with the name of a NUTS-3 region and asked to classify it as belonging to either “East Germany” or “West Germany” (See Listing 1). The prompt is intentionally minimal to avoid introducing contextual bias. All prompts are executed with temperature set to 0 to ensure deterministic outputs and minimize stochastic variation. This setup isolates the models’ internalized geographic knowledge rather than their generative variability. Model responses are then compared to the ground truth labels. Performance is evaluated using overall accuracy, recall, and F1-score, with particular attention to misclassifications.

2.2. Embedding-Based Similarity Analysis

In addition to discrete classification, we analyze whether latent semantic representations encode the former inner-German border. Hence, we use the `text-embedding-3-large` model to generate vector representations of region names as well as the reference concepts “East Germany” and “West Germany”. Cosine similarity is computed between each region embedding and both reference embeddings. This results in two similarity scores per region: similarity to East Germany and similarity to West Germany. We then compute a continuous difference score (East minus West similarity), which allows us to visualize gradual transitions across space. Furthermore, we derive a dominant affiliation by selecting the higher of the two similarity scores as the model’s dominant representation of the region.

3. Results

To evaluate the spatial structure of the model outputs, we map both (1) discrete classifications (LLM predictions and embedding-based dominant affiliation) and (2) continuous similarity differences. These maps are compared to the historical East–West boundary to assess whether a spatial discontinuity aligns with the former border.

Figure 1: The LLMs representations of East and West Germany at NUTS-3 Level.

3.1. LLM Classification Performance

All evaluated models achieve classification accuracy significantly above a random baseline. This indicates that the observed patterns are not due to chance and LLMs encode substantial knowledge about the historical East–West division. However, performance is not uniform across models. Some models exhibit systematic biases, such as a tendency to overpredict East Germany. Misclassifications are higher in DeepSeek-Chat. This shows that model knowledge may be influenced by uneven representation in training data. LLM classification provides a clear and interpretable decision while introduces sharper boundaries and occasional misclassifications. Figure ?? shows the LLMs’ predictions in classifying each region to either “East Germany” or “West Germany”. The results show that almost all models correctly classify the regions’ historical affiliation except GPT-4o and DeepSeek-chat. GPT-4o misclassifies two regions: Börde which is in East but classified as West and Hof (kreisfreie Stadt) which is in West and misclassified as East). DeepSeek-chat is the worst model since it misclassifies many regions in the historical “West Germany” as “East Germany”.

We then measure the performance of LLMs using classical machine learning metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. Table 1 shows how well a model represents the historical inner-German division. These metrics are 1.0 for most models, while GPT-4o shows slightly lower performance (0.99) and DeepSeek-chat exhibits substantially weaker results with the overall accuracy

of 0.75, precision of 0.44 for East and recall of 0.69 for West and F1-scores of 0.61 and 0.82 for East and West, respectively. This reveals that the newer models tried to improve their limitations in capturing historical spatial patterns.

Table 1

The performance of LLMs in representing the historical East-West German border.

Model	Overall Accuracy	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
GPT-5.4	1.00	E	1.0	1.0	1.0
		W	1.0	1.0	1.0
GPT-4o	0.99	E	0.99	0.99	0.99
		W	1.0	1.0	1.0
Gemini-3.1-pro-preview	1.00	E	1.0	1.0	1.0
		W	1.0	1.0	1.0
Gemini-2-flash	1.00	E	1.0	1.0	1.0
		W	1.0	1.0	1.0
DeepSeek-v4-pro	1.00	E	1.0	1.0	1.0
		W	1.0	1.0	1.0
DeepSeek-chat	0.75	E	0.44	1.0	0.61
		W	1.0	0.69	0.82
Text-embedding-3-large	0.79	E	0.48	0.96	0.64
		W	0.99	0.75	0.85

3.2. Embedding-Based Spatial Pattern

The embedding-based analysis reveals a spatial gradient in similarity scores. Regions in the former East Germany show higher similarity to “East Germany”, while regions in West Germany exhibit higher similarity to “West Germany”. However, there are still a notable number of regions in “West Germany” that show higher similarity to “East Germany” in the embedding space. When mapped, the continuous similarity difference shows a relatively clear spatial discontinuity that aligns with the historical inner-German border. This indicates that although the embedding space captures the general pattern, it does not fully encode the latent geographic structure of the phantom border. Unlike the LLM results, the embedding approach shows more nuanced spatial variation and reveals the gradual transition, highlighting areas where the distinction between East and West is less pronounced.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, we examined whether LLMs can represent the phantom border between East and West Germany. Using a prompt-based classification approach and an embedding-based similarity analysis, we find that the latest representations of LLMs can reproduce the historical division at the NUTS-3 level. The results provide strong evidence that phantom borders are not only present in socioeconomic or traditional spatial data, but are also embedded in the semantic structures learned from large-scale text corpora by modern GenAI systems. While classification results reveal explicit knowledge, embedding similarities uncover latent structures that are otherwise difficult to observe. This difference suggests that discrete LLM outputs reflect more explicit and possibly “*memorized*” associations, while embeddings capture more diffuse and context-dependent semantic relationships.

One important implication is that LLMs do not merely store factual geographic knowledge but also internalize historically contingent spatial patterns— which likely arise from the way regions are discussed in media narratives, historical content, and culturally specific discourse— embedded in language. However, the observed misclassifications in old models show some limitations. For example, these models struggle with regions where historical identity is less clearly represented in text. This indicates that model knowledge is uneven and influenced by data availability and representation biases.

Figure 2: The embedding representations of East and West Germany at NUTS-3 Level.

A limitation of this study is that region names themselves may carry implicit geographic signals, which could partially explain the high classification performance.

At the same time, if LLMs encode traces of so-called phantom borders, they may also reproduce spatial divisions that are historically contingent or no longer socially relevant. While our results are exploratory and do not directly assess downstream impacts, this raises questions for applications such as regional analysis or location-based systems, where representations of space can influence interpretation and decision-making. Hence, it is important to take a closer look at how AI systems understand and represent geography. As Janowicz [11] argues, AI systems are not neutral when it comes to representing geographic space. This makes it essential to carefully evaluate their outputs, so they do not reinforce existing inequalities, while still maintaining sound and reliable analysis. These findings highlight the importance of critically assessing how AI systems encode and reproduce geographic knowledge. Future work should apply similar methods to other historical boundaries and examine how different kinds of training data shape these patterns. It will also be important to develop methods to reduce or correct

these effects, so AI systems do not unintentionally preserve outdated views of the world.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Generative AI models to collect the LLMs predictions through their APIs. The authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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